

Recurrent Nasal Pterigium

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Clinical Image

A 69-year-old otherwise healthy patient, with a history of pterygium excision and an 11×6 mm conjunctival autograft secured with Tisseel fibrin glue in the left eye three months prior, presented for postoperative evaluation following phacoemulsification and intraocular lens implantation performed the previous day.

Corrected visual acuity was 0.3 LogMAR. Slit-lamp biomicroscopy revealed a recurrent nasal pterygium, an old corneal leukoma, and minimal corneal edema. The patient was maintained on topical antibiotic and anti-inflammatory therapy and was additionally prescribed lubricating eye drops as needed.

A conservative approach was adopted, with close monitoring of the pterygium's progression. Surgical excision of the recurrent lesion will be considered should the fibrovascular tissue extend to involve the pupillary zone.

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Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The Authors declare(s) that there is no conflict of interest.

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Figure 1: Pterigium.